

**TECHNOLOGIZATION OF THE CONTENT OF EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS
IN NEW UZBEKISTAN IS A REQUIREMENT OF THE TIME****Tleubaev Islambek Shamuratovich**teacher – methodist of the Tashkent regional training center
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Abstract: *This article is aimed at systematizing the norms governing educational activities, as well as adapting the content of educational materials in higher education to standards that meet the requirements of the times, further strengthening the knowledge and level of the younger generation.*

Key words: *education, norms, materials, higher education, technologization and consciousness.*

Annotatsiya: *Mazkur maqola ta'lim faoliyatini tartibga soluvchi normalarni tizimlashtirish shuningdek, oliy ta'limdagi o'quv materiallar mazmunini zamon talabiga javob beruvchi normalarga moslashtirish, yosh avlodni bilim va saviyasini yanada mustahkamlashga yo'naltirilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *ta'lim, norma, materiallar, oliy ta'lim, texnologiyalashtirish va ong.*

Аннотация: *Данная статья направлена на систематизацию норм, регулирующих образовательную деятельность, а также адаптацию содержания учебных материалов в высшем образовании к нормам, отвечающим требованиям времени, дальнейшее укрепление знаний и уровня молодого поколения.*

Ключевые слова: *образование, нормы, материалы, высшее образование, технологизация и сознание.*

“It is clear to all that both the cornerstone of development and the power that makes the country powerful and the nation great are science, education and education. Tomorrow, the bright prospect of our homeland, first of all, the educational system and it is closely related to the upbringing we give our children, “ says the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev [1].

Indeed, an intellectual citizen of each country lives his life in science and without the progress of education can not imagine. Because, as if humanity is spinning around the axis of

science. It is also not for nothing that the development of education in the leading countries of the world is defined as a task in the first Gal. It is in this area that the future prosperity of the country is closely related to its achievements.

Today, the educational activities of universities are further improved, and the quality of our people's pursuit of Science, which has been formed over the centuries, is once again manifested. To live a healthy and beautiful life for our young people, to have a permanent job in the profession we occupy, to take responsibility, to belittle human dignity avoiding, in short, is trying to achieve perfection and in this process, learning is seen as the most basic condition.

In order to further improve similar reforms in the new Uzbekistan, the adoption of the Law No. 901 "on the status of an educator", adopted on February 1, 2024, indicates that the implementation of constitutional norms is ensured above all[2]. At the same time, regulatory legal acts were adopted in the country, regulating educational activities in about 50 areas of education in order to regulate relations in the field of Education.

These include: - management of the educational system; - transfer of educational organizations from attestation and state accreditation; - state educational standards and requirements; - state educational institutions and organizations; - non - governmental educational organizations; - educational institutions and organizations of foreign countries; - educational types; - secondary education; - legal status of educators and other employees of educational organizations; - admission to educational institutions, transfer of education, exclusion and reinstatement of Summer rest of children; - practice. Internship; - Olympiads and competitions; - qualification. Retraining; - state educational standards. Educational programs. Educational process; - educational institutions; - model regulations on educational institutions; - Financing of educational institutions, provision of material equipment and state support;-certification and accreditation of educational institutions; - secondary - special vocational education (lyceums, Colleges);-Higher Education (undergraduate and graduate);-post - higher education (postgraduate, ad'yunktura, doctoral, research); - other types of Education. Additional (extracurricular) education; - non-governmental educational institutions (educational institutions of private, public associations, religious and other organizations). Licensing the activities of non - governmental and religious educational institutions; - children's homes. Work with minors; - pedagogical personnel. Certification of pedagogical personnel; - Documents on education; - admission to educational institutions, transfer, exclusion and reinstatement of studies; - admission of foreign citizens to educational institutions; - sending citizens to study abroad; - the rights and social protection of Students, Students and educators; - state grants. Education of

citizens in need of Social Protection; - pay-contract education; - material and domestic provision of students and students; -scholarships; - textbooks, teaching aids and educational tools; - holidays. Summer rest of children; - practice. Interns; - provision of paid educational services; - individual pedagogical activity; - social protection of Educational Personnel; - Olympics. Norms such as choices include.

These norms today serve to provide a legal basis for technologization in the country not only through the systematization of educational activities, but also educational materials in it. In particular, at present, technologies based on the achievements of physics, chemistry, Energy, Biology, Mathematics, Computer Science and other sciences have brought about a technological revolution.

The technological approach in the field of production - the presentation of production processes as technology - has become an indispensable feature of modern material production. It acts as a cumulative expression of the level of development achieved, the introduction of the achievements of science into practice, the most important indicator of high professionalism of activity.

With the introduction of state standards of general education in the school, the requirements for the results of the study of meta-subjects as a new methodological approach also change the requirements for the teacher. A teacher who is well versed in teaching technologies can develop meta-subject competencies of the learners.

A brief description of educational technology can be presented in the following structure[3].

1. The essence of technology, reflecting the main problem being solved, the main qualities, the main idea, the essence of the educational system being used and, finally, the main direction of the development of the educational process.

2. Targeted areas of technology. The target system is the core that holds the technology together and faces it. Referring to the category of "goal" characterizes the position, orientation of a person in relation to a certain area of development. Technology describes the goals and objectives that are planned to achieve and solve.

3. Conceptual foundations of pedagogical technology. It is a brief description of the basic ideas and principles of technology, facilitating the understanding and interpretation of its structure and operation. Including philosophical positions, applied factors and laws of development, the assimilation of experience scientific concept and methods of training used.

4. Organizational characteristics of technology modern ideas of Education

and theories, principles of consistency, are considered in terms of the compliance of goals with social orders.

5. Procedural descriptions (methodological features of technology). The complex application and interaction of all methodological tools, the features of methodology, diagnostics and planning are determined.

6. Educational and methodological support (educational plans and programs, educational and methodological manuals, didactic, assessment materials, visual teaching and technical means)[4].

Technologization of teaching is the direction of pedagogical science that studies and opens up the laws and principles, convenient ways and means of effectively achieving educational goals on the basis of a technological approach to the process of learning and development of students.

Pedagogical technology is defined as the field of knowledge about the design activities, which, using the language of technological procedures of the design, defines the pedagogical position, pedagogical plan, allows you to translate pedagogical ideas about a particular pedagogical object into a project form that can be implemented in educational practice.

In a broader sense, teaching technology consists of:

- design and presentation of planned educational results;
- the creation and use of diagnostic tools for educational achievements of students of Educational Sciences and the development of competencies:
 - set of training models, tools and methods to increase cognitive activity;
 - criteria for choosing a favorable model for certain educational conditions;
 - extensive use of computer and audiovisual technical means, active forms of teaching, modern organization of the educational process and independent work.

Objects of technologization in educational activities should be:

- goals;
- content;
- content;
- organizational methods of perception, processing and presentation of information;
- forms of interaction between the subjects of educational activities, their personal and professional behavior, self-management and creative development procedures.

Products of technological development of the educational process personal, social and there may be professionally relevant algorithms and stereotypes of the behavior of educators. This ensures the success and competitiveness of graduates of educational organizations.

Signs of the technological efficiency of the educational process:

- detailed description of educational goals;
- step-by-step description (design) of methods for achieving the specified results;
- transmission, presentation, perception of educational and socio-cultural information, systematic use of psychological, pedagogical and technical means of processing;
- systematic use of feedback for the purpose of determining and evaluating the effectiveness of the educational process;
- guarantee of achieved results;
- repetition of the learning process, regardless of the skill of the teacher;
- optimal ratio of resources and forces spent.

Technological efficiency of the educational process, as well as quality and assessment of educational activities of the educational organization and in general, its economic efficiency and is considered as one of the indicators of ensuring a humanitarian direction.

In this regard, it acts both as a norm for the design of the educational process and as a set of steps of participants in methodological, didactic, psychological, intellectual, informational and practical actions, operations, techniques, educational relations, specially developed for the intended purpose. guarantee the freedom to achieve established educational goals and choose them consciously[5].

The main didactic ideas of technologization, taking into account the competency-based approach, should take into account:

- guarantees of achieving the final result;
- universality for any educational organization, any subject of study, any teacher, any student;
- development of a technological map for the entire period of study in each discipline through the micromaxad system;
- competencies;
- setting diagnostic goals in competency categories defined in the educational program;
- diagnostics-the idea that at each stage of training the learner has achieved or has not achieved the requirements of the curriculum;
- technologization-as new opportunities for purposeful, impartial and fair accurate management of the educational process and its quality according to its final results.

Using new organizational forms:

- training expeditions;
- ability tournament (meta-science Olympics);
- organizational and active games;
- projects;
- network projects;
- workshops;
- trainings;
- meta-topic lesson;
- meta-topic workshop;
- reflexive training;
- lesson status.

With the technologization of education, the status of the teacher changes: the information transmitter becomes the administrator of the educational process. The design of the educational process is the most labor-intensive of the teacher and is one of his responsible work.

In this regard, the teacher is considered not only as a specialist in a particular field of science, but, above all, as a teacher-manager or director, a person personally responsible for the educational process and for himself, responsible for the consequences of educational results.

A teacher who does not have his own professional experience cannot effectively organize educational activities to master the profession[6]. Educational goals, changing the content and forms is noticeable to the nature of communication between teachers and educators, the environment of their interaction effect.

Cooperation, equality of individuals in choice, actions, responsibility, a positive emotional environment - all of them become a constant dominant of the forms of relations and interaction between students and teachers, as well as between each other.

The novelty of approaches in the context of competency-based education requires that teachers themselves learn the following:

- algorithm for working on new organizational forms of the lesson;
- methods/techniques to make the activities of learners problematic;
- consulting techniques;
- technology for assessing the level of development of educational competencies.

This requires experience in the following:

- development of the project concept as part of the group;
- the beginning and methods of stimulating the labor of educators;

- support as leader;
- assessment of the level of development of results on competencies;
- assessment of the capabilities of the subject for the formation of competencies;
- Mastering technologies for the development and application of COT (competency-oriented tasks), using the Case Study method (analysis of specific situations), projects, work and simulation games and other active forms. The use of active forms of educational organization, the use of modern pedagogical technologies in the implementation of the state educational standard, the formation of competencies of Education recipients and can be considered as one of the main methods of development.

Literature used:

1. Online newspaper “Xalq so‘zi” of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
2. National bleeding base of the Republic of Uzbekistan // lex.uz.
3. Selevko G.K. Sovremennie obrazovatelnie tehnologii: uchebnoe posobie. M.: Narodnoe obrazovanie, 1998, - p.61–62.
4. This source. - P. 64.
5. Monakhov V.M. Vvedenie V teoriyu pedagogicheskix tehnologiy. Monograph. Volgograd. Peremena, 2006, p.319.
6. Yefremova N.F. Kompetentsii V obrazovanii: formirovanie i otsenivanie. M.: Nasionalnoe obrazovanie, 2012, p.173.